

hydrolysis; it is superimposable to that of authentic apigenin-8-C-glucoside (vitexin). Identity as vitexin⁶ confirmed by co-tlc (R_f : 78, 69 in the same order of solvents as A) with authentic sample.

Compound C: Light yellow solid, m.p. 210-12°; R_f : 58, 45 (PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} : almost the same as for A (in MeOH, NaOAc and AlCl₃); gave orientin (A) and D-glucose in 1:1 ratio on treatment with 2 N HCl or β -glucosidase. C was characterised as orientin-O'-glucoside and was indistinguishable from orientin-2'-O-glucoside⁷ by co-tlc (R_f : 28, 43) with an authentic sample.

Compound D: Light yellow solid, m.p. 216-18°; R_f : 69, 50 (PC, 15% HOAc, BAW); λ_{max} almost identical with B; yielded vitexin (B) and D-glucose in 1:1 ratio by acid as well as enzyme hydrolysis. D was characterised as vitexin-O'-glucoside and was indistinguishable from vitexin-2'-O-glucoside⁷ by co-tlc (R_f : 46, 57) with an authentic sample. (Owing to paucity of material, MS of the permethyl ether of C and D could not be run to fully establish their identities with orientin and vitexin-2'-glucosides).

M. cerviana resembles other *Mollugo* species in biosynthesising C-glycosyl flavones. However, in the place of 2'-rhamnosides of flavone-C-glucoside and arabinoside of *M. disticha* and mono and di-C-pentosyl flavones of *M. pentaphylla*, we have isolated the two common glycoflavones, orientin and vitexin along with their rare 2'-O-glucosides whose occurrence was earlier reported in *Cannabis sativa*⁸.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) with 3-Bromo-2-Hydroxy-5-Methylacetophenone Hydrazone (BHMAH)

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A systematic spectrophotometric study of some transition metal ions complexes of 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (BHMA) and its oxime were undertaken by us with a view to investigate their chelating and other properties^{1,2}. In this note we report the use of 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone hydrazone (BHMAH) for spectrophotometric determination of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II).

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: Absorbance and pH measurements were carried out as reported earlier³. Standard stock solutions of metal ions were prepared in distilled water as described earlier³.

The ligand, BHMAH, was synthesized by refluxing BHMA¹ (0.1 mol) with hydrazinium sulphate (0.1 mol) in ethanolic medium for ~ 2 hr. The product was poured in water, filtered and crystallized from acetone, m.p. 220°. The purity of the BHMAH was checked by tlc and elemental analyses. (Found: C, 44.56; H, 4.50; N, 11.47; Br, 32.90. Calcd. for C₉H₁₁N₂OBr; C, 44.44; H, 4.52; N, 11.52; Br, 32.92%). The solution of BHMAH was prepared by dissolving on appropriate amount of the reagent in acetone.

Sodium perchlorate (Reidel) was used to maintain the ionic strength. All other solutions of cations and anions were prepared by dissolving A. R. grade chemicals in distilled water.

Procedure: An aliquot of the test solution (containing 30-50 μ g of metal ion) is transferred to a 100 ml measuring flask and excess of BHMAH solution in acetone is added. The pH of the solution is adjusted (Table 1) using suitable buffer. The total volume is made upto the mark maintaining 75% (v/v) acetone medium. The absorbance is recorded at 400 nm with the reagent solution as the blank. The amount of the metal ion is calculated from a previously calibrated graph.

Results and Discussion

Absorbance curves: The absorbance spectra show that the metal complexes in acetone show maximum absorbance at 400 nm.

Effect of acidity and reagent concentration: A series of solutions (metal:ligand in 1:8) varying in pH was prepared and the absorbances were recorded at 400 nm. The optimum acidity range for the complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF CHELATES OF Cu(II), Ni(II) AND Co(II) WITH BHMAH

Characteristics	Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Co(II)
Colour	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow
λ_{\max} (nm)	400	400	400
pH range	5.0-6.0	8.5-10.5	2.0-6.0
Composition (metal : ligand)	1 : 1	1 : 2	1 : 2
Degree of dissociation	0.630	0.551	0.437
Log stability constant	3.970	8.224	8.228
Beer's law range (ppm)	0.18-2.75	0.37-2.6	0.62-6.22
Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.013	0.0124	0.0155
Molar absorptivity ($\text{l.mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	4800	4720	3790
Standard deviation (from 10 samples)	0.062	0.051	0.068

The colour development was also studied by varying the reagent concentration from 0.5-16 times (fold excess w.r.t. metal ion). The optimum range of reagent concentration needed for full colour development was found to be 8 times excess of the metal ion. The colour develops immediately on addition of the reagent and the complex is stable for more than 18 hr at room temperature.

Beer's law, optimum range and molar absorptivity: Test solutions with different concentrations of metal ion were prepared by the recommended procedure. The system adhered to Beer's plots and showed the optimum range for the determination of metal^a. The relative error for this range was 2.5%. The molar absorptivity was found and reported in Table 1. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reaction is also reported in Table 1 at 400 nm.

Composition of the complex: The metal : ligand composition in the metal complexes under study was determined by the method of continuous⁴, mole ratio⁵ and slope ratio⁶ methods utilizing equimolar and non-equimolar solutions of the metal and reagent. All these methods indicate the 1 : 2 metal : ligand ratio in the complexes of Ni(II) and Co(II) and 1 : 1 metal : ligand ratio in the complex of Cu(II) at 400 nm.

Degree of dissociation and stability constant: The overall stability constant has been calculated by following the mole ratio method. The degree of dissociation has been obtained from the relation $\alpha = (E_m - E_s)/E_m$ where E_m is the maximum absorbance and E_s is the absorbance corresponding to the inflexion point in mole ratio graph. The stability constant K was obtained from the equations $K = (1 - \alpha)/C\alpha^2$ and $K = (1 - \alpha)/4C^2\alpha^3$ for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes, respectively where C is actual concentration of the metal complexes. The values are reported in Table 1 at an ionic strength 0.1 M (NaClO₄) in 75% (v/v) acetone.

Effect of foreign ions: The influence of foreign ions on the estimation of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) using BHMAH was also studied. The tolerance limits for the foreign ions (ppm, given in parentheses) which did not cause deviation of more than $\pm 2.5\%$ in absorbance are given below.

Cu(II) (30 μg): Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻, CH₃COO⁻ (1000, each); NO₂⁻ (500); I⁻ (100); citrate, tartrate (25, each); Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cr³⁺, Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺ (500, each); Pb²⁺, Fe²⁺ (200, each). However, Pd²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Fe³⁺, PO₄³⁻, BO₃³⁻ and CNS⁻ were found to interfere.

Ni(II) (30 μg): Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻ (1000, each); CNS⁻, NH₄⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺ (500, each); Ca²⁺, Zn²⁺, Fe²⁺ (100, each); Hg²⁺, Al³⁺ (50, each) could be tolerated. However, Pd²⁺, Co²⁺, Fe³⁺ and BO₃³⁻ were found to interfere.

Co(II) (50 μg): Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻, SO₄²⁻, SO₃²⁻ (1000, each); PO₄³⁻, BO₃³⁻, C₂O₄²⁻, CNS⁻ (500, each); Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺ (400, each); Al³⁺, Cr³⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, Fe²⁺ (200, each); Th⁴⁺, Mo⁶⁺, W⁶⁺, Zr⁴⁺ (100, each) could be tolerated. However, Pd²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Fe³⁺ and EDTA were found to interfere.

Precision and accuracy: A number of measurements (10 samples) were taken at a given concentra-

TABLE 2—COMPARATIVE STUDY OF BHMAH WITH OTHER REAGENTS

Reagents	λ_{\max} (nm)	Beer's law range (ppm)	Molar absorptivity ($\text{l. mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	Ref.
Cu(II)					
2-Hydroxyacetophenone oxime	355	1-6 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	3400	0.0187	7
2,4-Dihydroxyvalerophenone oxime	640	45-80	162	0.393	8
Salicylaldehyde hydrazone	400	0.93-4.41	7800	0.008	9
BHMAH	400	0.18-2.75	4800	0.013	present work
Ni(II)					
2-Hydroxyacetophenone oxime	375	1-6 ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	4100	0.014	10
2,4-Dihydroxyvalerophenone oxime	590	98-70	160	0.367	8
Phenanthraquinone monoxime	450	3.5-21.3	5950	0.098	11
2-Hydroxyacetophenone hydrazone	425	2.9-9.6	734	0.08	9
BHMAH	400	0.37-2.6	4720	0.0124	present work
Co(II)					
Salicylaldehyde hydrazone	450	1.6-4.6	7900	0.0074	9
BHMAH	400	0.62-6.22	3790	0.0155	present work

tion (usually 3 different concentrations). In the measurement of the metal ion concentration, standard deviation was found to be 0.05 to 0.07 ppm and percentage relative error was found to be 0.1-0.3%.

A comparative study with other reagents, recently used for the metals under study (Table 2) was undertaken and it was found that the BHMAH is a better reagent.

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Use of 2-Hydroxy-4-Ethoxyacetophenone Oxime (HEAO) as Analytical Reagent : Studies on Nickel Chelate

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MANY reagents¹⁻³ have been used for the determination of nickel. In continuation of our work on the use of 2-hydroxy-4-ethoxyacetophenone oxime (HEAO) as a reagent for copper⁴, we have used it as a gravimetric reagent for nickel.

The reagent gives green precipitate of nickel chelate quantitatively in the pH range 5.5 to 9.0. The chelate is insoluble in alcohol, ether and acetic acid but is soluble in chloroform. There are advantages in using this reagent over other reagents⁴.

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Determination of nickel : Gravimetric determination of nickel in different aliquots at pH 5.5-6.0 was carried out according to the method described earlier⁴. The error in any case did not exceed $\pm 0.3\%$.

Cations like Zn(II), Pb(II), Cd(II), Sr(II), Mg(II), Mn(II) and Al(III) and anions like chloride, nitrate, bromide, sulphate, tartrate and citrate were found not to interfere in the gravimetric determination of nickel at pH 5.5-6.0. The error in any case was not greater than $\pm 0.7\%$. The interference due to Fe(II) and Fe(III) was removed using sequestering agents like potassium citrate or Rochelle salt. Co(II) chelate coprecipitates with nickel chelate at pH 6.0, but as the cobalt chelate is soluble in alcohol it can be removed during washing of the nickel chelate with alcohol. The reagent was used to determine copper(II) and nickel(II) in binary mixture by working at controlled pH. The results were reproducible.

Structure of nickel chelate : The nickel chelate was analysed for carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and metal content. The results correspond to $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3\text{N})_2$. Metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2 was also confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation.

The visible spectra of nickel chelate in chloroform gives a strong band at 375 nm. Nickel chelate was found to be diamagnetic showing the absence of unpaired electron. Ni(II) has d^8 configuration and hence it conforms to square planar structure.

IR spectra of nickel chelate shows the band at $2900-3000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (=N-OH group). The band appearing at 3400 cm^{-1} (phenolic -OH group) in oxime disappeared in chelate. The bands due to $\nu\text{ C}=\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{ NO}$ appeared at lower frequency in chelate than those in ligand⁵.

On the basis of the above evidences the following structure is suggested for the nickel chelate.

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